

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Isobutyric Acid by Ce(IV) in Aqueous Nitric Acid Solutions

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Kinetic study of oxidation of isobutyric acid by cerium (IV) in aqueous solutions of nitric acid shows that the reaction follows first order kinetics in both Ce(IV) and isobutyric acid and the overall reaction order ascertained is two. Effects of hydrogen ions concentration, temperature and ionic strength of the medium have been examined in details. Ionic strength and nitrate ions have negative effects on reaction rate which is independent of the concentration of hydrogen ions. A suitable mechanism consistent with the kinetic results has been suggested. Activation parameters have also been computed.

Ce(IV) has been widely used as an oxidant in oxidation of many substrates in sulphuric acid medium¹⁻¹⁶. Its oxidising capacity attains higher magnitude when it is used in nitric and perchloric acids because of its comparatively increased oxidation potential in latter acids. The use of latter acids becomes essential when Ce(IV) is found, sometimes, ineffective oxidant in sulphuric acid. Isobutyric acid was found to be unoxidised with ceric sulphate in sulphuric acid solution but was found to be oxidised by Ce(IV) in nitric acid solutions. The present paper aims at finding out a suitable mechanism for the oxidation of isobutyric acid by ceric ammonium nitrate in aqueous solutions of nitric acid on the basis of kinetic results.

Materials and Procedure

Isobutyric acid (Riedel) was distilled in a quick fit apparatus and the fraction collected at 154.4° was employed. Ceric ammonium nitrate, ceric sulphate, nitric acid and ferrous ammonium sulphate were all (BDH) A.R. grade chemicals. Other chemicals used were either (BDH) or (Riedel) grade.

A stock solution of ceric sulphate was prepared by usual method. Ceric ammonium nitrate solution was prepared by direct weighing and standardised against the standard solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate using ferroin as redox indicator.

The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating the amounts of remaining Ce(IV) at different intervals of time. The requisite volumes of standard solutions of ceric ammonium nitrate, nitric acid and water were taken in 100 ml conical flask (coated with black Japan from outside) kept in a thermostat maintained at desired temperature. Requisite volume of isobutyric acid, maintained at

the same temperature in a separate flask, was added to the solution of first flask. The kinetics were followed by removing 5 ml aliquots after suitable intervals and adding it to a known excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate solution. The excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate was estimated with the help of a standard solution of ceric sulphate using ferroin as redox indicator. The method gave always reproducible results.

Results and Discussion

Dependence of reaction on oxidant: In order to determine the order of reaction with respect to the oxidant, the reaction was studied at different initial concentrations of ceric ammonium nitrate and at fixed concentrations of other reactants. The reaction follows first order kinetics in Ce(IV). Table 1

TABLE 1

Time in min.	Temperature 45°	
	[HNO ₃] = 2.0N	[Ceric ammonium nitrate] = 2.00 × 10 ⁻³ N
	[Iso butyric acid] = 40.00 × 10 ⁻² M	
	Volume of ceric sulphate (1.6 × 10 ⁻³ N) required by 5 ml. of the reaction mixture	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
0	3.70	—
10	4.50	13.87
20	4.88	10.59
35	5.80	11.84
50	6.48	11.95
60	7.12	13.44
75	7.36	11.96
95	7.84	11.67
115	8.16	11.13
130	8.36	10.79
145	8.60	10.86
	9.88	—

Average value of k₁ = 11.81 × 10⁻³min⁻¹

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contains the representative results obtained in a set of the reaction. The results of other studies, done at different concentrations of Ce(IV), are given in Table 2. The k_1 (first order rate constant) values obtained from the slopes of the curves (Pseudo first order plots are not given) were also given in Table 2 and show good agreement with average k_1 values. Contrary to our expectation, the k_1 values decrease with increasing initial concentrations of Ce(IV). Shorter¹⁰ and Bhagwat⁹ also noted similar effect in their studies. This behaviour of the reaction may be attributed to the formation of some unreactive polymeric ceric species at higher ceric concentrations. Hardwick and Robertson¹⁷ also suggested dimerisation of dehydrolysed ceric species in perchloric acid solutions and represented the equilibrium as

A plot of k_1 values against $1/[\text{Ce(IV)}]$ gives a straight line (Fig. 1) which does not pass through origin, which provides a positive evidence for the formation of some unreactive complex at higher ceric concentrations.

Fig. 1. Temperature 45°
[Iso butyric acid] = 40.00 × 10⁻² M
[HNO₃] = 2.00 N

Dependence of reaction on reducing substrate: In order to find out the order of reaction with respect to the reductant, the reaction was studied at different concentrations of isobutyric acid by isolation method. The results are recorded in Table 2. Pseudo-first order plots in Ce(IV) at different concentrations of isobutyric acid (Fig. 2) are given and k_1 values from these plots are recorded in Table 2. A perusal of data of Table 2 indicates that k_1 (first order constants) values are directly proportional to the concentrations of isobutyric acid showing thereby that the reaction also follows first order kinetics in isobutyric acid. The values of k_2 (second order rate constant) calculated from $k_1/[\text{Isobutyric acid}]$ are practically

constant (last column of Table 2). The average k_2 value at 45° in 2N HNO₃ is 3.04 × 10⁻² mole⁻¹ min⁻¹

TABLE 2
Temperature 45°
[HNO₃] = 2.0N

[Ceric ammonium nitrate] × 10 ³ N	[Iso butyric acid] × 10 ² M	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{min}^{-1}$		$k_2 \times 10^2 \text{l. mole}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$
		Average	Graphical	
1.00	40.00	28.00	27.16	—
1.25	"	19.04	18.96	—
1.60	"	16.06	16.18	—
2.00	"	11.81	11.78	—
2.50	"	10.46	10.61	—
5.00	"	6.39	6.42	—
2.00	5.00	1.72	1.68	3.44
"	10.00	3.06	3.17	3.06
"	25.00	6.83	6.90	2.73
"	30.00	9.34	8.55	3.13
"	40.00	11.81	12.79	2.95
"	45.00	13.32	14.30	2.96

Average value of $k_2 = 3.04 \times 10^{-2} \text{l. mole}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$

which is nearly identical with the average value of k_2 i.e., 3.09 l mole⁻¹ min⁻¹ obtained from Fig. 2, proving thereby the first order dependence of the reaction on isobutyric acid.

Fig. 2. Temperature 45°
[Ceric ammonium nitrate] = 2.00 × 10⁻³ N, [HNO₃] = 2.00 N
[Iso-butyric acid] =

A = 5.00 × 10 ⁻² M	A → 33.60
B = 10.00 × 10 ⁻² M	B → 31.10
C = 25.00 × 10 ⁻² M	C → 27.60
D = 30.00 × 10 ⁻² M	D → 28.50
E = 40.00 × 10 ⁻² M	E → 31.97
F = 45.00 × 10 ⁻² M	F → 31.98

From graph
 $k_2 \times 10^3 \text{l. mole}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$

Effect of hydrogen ions, nitrate ions and ionic strength: The results obtained at different ionic strengths of the medium (adjusted by adding different amounts of NaCl₄) show retarding effect on the reaction rate. It is not possible to explain the retarding effect of ionic strength here under the conditions of Table 3 where Debye-Huckel limiting law fails. In view of effect of ionic strength on the reaction rate, it was thought proper to study the effect of hydrogen ions, nitrate ions at constant ionic strength of the medium. The effect of hydrogen ions was studied changing the concentration of nitric acid. The result (Table 3) indicates the retarding effect of nitric acid at constant ionic strength. This effect is due to the combined effect of hydrogen and nitrate ions. Hence, in order to obtain the effect of hydrogen ions on rate of the reaction, the reaction was studied at various concentrations of perchloric acid and at fixed concentrations of nitrate ions. The results of Table 3 clearly indicate that the reaction rate is

activation (ΔE) and entropy of activation (ΔS) are 17.48 K.cal/mole and -10.84 E.U. respectively. The values of free energy (ΔF) and frequency factor (A) come out to be 20.94 K.cal/mole and 7.69×10^{10} l. mole⁻¹ min⁻¹ respectively. Stoichiometry studies have shown that in Ce(IV)-isobutyric acid reaction about 8 equivalents of Ce(IV) are consumed per mole of isobutyric acid. Acetic and formic acids have been identified as products and have been tested by chromatographic technique.

A parusal of Ce(IV) oxidation of substrates in aqueous nitric acid suggests that effects of H⁺ and NO₃⁻ are the real factors that decide the reactive species of Ce(IV) in nitric acid solution. Our kinetic observations suggest us to assume that Ce(OH)³⁺ is a predominant oxidising species. The reaction, thus follows the following scheme :

(C)

This scheme leads to a rate expression as

$$\text{rate} = -\frac{d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = k_2[\text{Ceric}][(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CHCOOH}] \quad \dots (4)$$

When isobutyric acid concentration is in large excess as compared to that of ceric then

$$\text{rate} = k_1[\text{Ceric}] \quad \dots (5)$$

Thus the rate expression is quite consistent with our kinetic data and fully explains that in Ce(IV) oxidation of isobutyric acid.

- (i) The reaction is first order with respect to Ce(IV).
- (ii) The reaction follows first order kinetics in isobutyric acid.
Thus total order of the reaction is two and
- (iii) The reaction rate is not influenced by hydrogen ions.

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TABLE 3

Ceric ammonium nitrate = $1.0 \times 10^{-3}N$
[Iso butyric acid] = $40.0 \times 10^{-2}M$

Temp. in °C	[HNO ₃]	Ionic strength (μ) M	[HClO ₄]	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{min}^{-1}$
45	1.00	1.01	—	82.12
"	"	1.05	—	74.42
"	"	1.21	—	59.00
"	"	1.41	—	39.78
"	"	1.61	—	26.95
45	0.75	3.00	—	70.72
"	1.00	"	—	49.71
"	1.25	"	—	40.54
"	2.00	"	—	34.46
"	2.50	"	—	26.70
45	1.00	3.00	0.2	46.24
"	"	"	0.4	46.29
"	"	"	0.6	46.30
"	"	"	0.8	46.36
"	"	"	1.2	47.00
45	"	"	1.6	46.19
"	"	"	2.0	46.34
40	2N	"	—	17.92
50	"	"	—	46.08
55	"	"	—	86.33

independent of hydrogen ion concentration. Perchlorate ions^{17,18} are well known to have no effect on reaction velocity. Therefore, the retarding effect of nitric acid is due to nitrate ions effect. The negative effect of nitrate ions may be explained due to conversion of Ce(OH)³⁺ into much less reactive species by complexation with nitrate ions as shown below :

Such effect has also been observed by earlier workers^{14,19,20}.

Results obtained at different temperatures are also noted in Table 3. The values of energy of

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